

Automated Detection of Prostate Cancer Nuclei

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ABSTRACT

In this work, a cross-disciplinary approach was presented for the solution of a biomedical pattern recognition problem: cancer diagnosis. Specifically, prostate specimen images were analyzed. Images were acquired by a microscope, video camera and a digitizing board and stored on a computer. The software required to indicate the areas of interest of the tissue image to the pathologist, was developed on the object-oriented basis. User interface was designed for the required functions. Discriminatory power of shape feature were evaluated statistically. The sensitivity and specificity ratios for different threshold levels of the feature set were calculated

1 INTRODUCTION

The early diagnosis of cancer is very important for complete treatment and saving life of a patient. The suspicious specimen is required to be inspected by a pathologist for the exact diagnosis. Microscopy is a labor-intensive, manual work and the pathologist requires great time and concentration [1,2].

Automated analysis systems aid the pathologist by identifying the areas of interest in the microscope image. Most important part is the detection of abnormal cells that were missed by the pathologist. Nowadays automated analysis systems are available in the market for the reinspection of smear specimens.

In this work, the analysis software was developed in document-view architecture using Visual C++ and MFC 4.0 [3,4]. In this way the user-friendly environment was created. The user can select the function or a series of functions that will be applied to the raw image and see the result on the screen. The program interface is given in figure 1.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Image Acquisition

The specimen images were x100 magnified by the Leica microscope. An oil immersion objective was used. The

analog image signal was acquired with a Sony color camera and with a s-video connection the signal was transmitted to the computer. The images were digitalised in 768x576 pixel 24bit/pixel format and saved.

2.2 Histology

Microscopic slices are the radical prostatectomy materials belonging to the patients who had a surgical operation because of prostate cancer. The radical prostatectomy materials were fixed in 10% formalin for 24-48 h. to preserve the biologic structure. Routine tissue inspection was applied to the entire structure. Paraffin blocks preped from the tissue cut into 5- μ m thick slices and stained with heamatoxylin and eosin.

2.3 Algorithm

In the first stage, the image was converted to 8 bit/pixel grey scale. After smoothing operation, the image was thresholded. The result image contains cell nuclei as well as other dark areas. Area contours were drawn by using region growing-combining and contour tracing algorithms [5]. For the elimination of inner contours that can be seen in the nucleus, control algorithm was implemented. After feature extraction, classification was performed. The flow diagram of the algorithm is given in figure 2.

Figure 1. Program interface

Figure 2. The flow diagram of the system

2.4 Features

For classification, a set of morphologic, statistical and colour features were calculated. These are

- The average distance of the contour pixels from the center of the contour:

$$d_{av} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n d_i \quad (1)$$

- Standard deviation of the distances:

$$s_d = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n-1} \sum_i (d_i - d_{av})^2} \quad (2)$$

- Circumference ratio:

$$c = \frac{2\pi \cdot d_{av}}{\text{number.of contour pixels}} \quad (3)$$

- Ratio of the axes: $d_o = \frac{d_{\max}}{d_T}$ (4)

- Average grey level: $a_{av} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i^n a_i$ (5)

Separation performance of the feature sets were calculated by using the quadratic distance measure.

3 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The features average distance and standard deviation of the distance were used for classification. Statistical data of the features for the areas that are nucleus and not nucleus was given in Table 1. Standard deviation vs average distance plot of nucleus and non-nucleus objects is given in figure 3.

Table 1. Statistical data of the features

nucleus?		d_{av}	s_d	c	d_o	a_{av}
✓	$\bar{x}$	30.1	3.84	1.03	1.86	67.6
✓	σ	5.6	3.28	.095	1.03	8.59
X	$\bar{x}$	30.7	14.7	0.92	16.9	77.3
X	σ	40.1	24.8	.199	36.1	8.03

Figure 3. s_d vs d_{av} plot nucleus and non-nucleus objects

Correct classification ratio depends on the threshold values of the feature set. Since the correct classification of all of the nuclei is more important than misclassification of a non-nucleus object [6,7,8], threshold values were calculated according to this. Results of classification with two different threshold sets was give in table 2. With the 1. set, 24 out of 35 nuclei was classified correctly (true +). With the 2. set in addition to all of the nuclei, 4 non-nucleus objects were classified as non-nucleus (false +). Objects images classified as nucleus were outlined and marked with a + sign on the display (figure 4).

Table 2. Classification results

Feature threshold set		
1	sensitivity	% 65.7 (24/35)
	specificity	% 84.8 (67/79)
	false +	% 1.27 (1/79)
2	sensitivity	% 100 (35/35)
	specificity	% 94.9 (75/79)
	false +	% 5.06 (4/79)

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Figure 4. Display of the analysis result

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